

Psychological Basis for Developing Responsible Attitude in Entrepreneurs

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Abstract:

The article presents a scientific and practical analysis to identify socio-psychological factors that develop the responsibility of interpersonal relations among entrepreneurs and improve the formation of relations of responsibility.

Keywords: entrepreneurship, interpersonal relations, responsibility, professional motivation.

In our country, fundamental reforms are being carried out in all areas. In particular, within the framework of the development of a market economy and entrepreneurship. Each developing country pays special attention to the development of a market economy. In this regard, the President of our Republic Sh. Mirziyoyev has developed and is implementing a number of decrees and resolutions. In accordance with the five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021, recommended by the President of our Republic Sh. Mirziyoyev, large-scale reforms aimed at improving the investment environment, creating a favorable business environment. and stimulating the rapid development of small businesses and private entrepreneurship.

In the conditions of a modern market economy, the essence of entrepreneurial activity lies in the extent to which it has mastered the art of managing interpersonal relationships, that is, organizing people into a team, planning, control, exchanging information, etc. In this process, the intellectual potential of entrepreneurs, persistence, satisfaction of the material and spiritual needs of people, their deep sense of responsibility and duty to the group, community and society are important.

The Republic of Uzbekistan is undergoing cardinal changes in all spheres, to become a friendly city in the middle of a leading development country. In private, it is possible to see in the interest of ensuring the operational development of entrepreneurial activity, comprehensive protection of private ownership, and quality improvement of the business environment [1].

And to this day, Uzbekistan is the leader of the state of Europe and Central Asia with the possibility of reform and the development of the business environment.

The approaches to the study of social interaction are analyzed taking into account the responsibility of the relationships of entrepreneurs within the framework of interaction of entrepreneurs. The study of mutual cooperation in various areas: the organization of mutual cooperation in the field of joint work was organized by A.Ya. Zhuravlev, K.K. Platonov, E.V. Those who analyzed in the studies of Shorokhova. L. Berkovits, V.A. Bodrov, D.M. Darley, L.I. Dementi, E.D. Dorofeev, B. Latane, K.D. Latterman, A.L. Lutsenko, K. Muzdybaev, M.V. Mukonina's theoretical approaches to understanding responsibility are covered in the development of conceptual ideas about the influence of relational responsibility on mutual cooperation of businessmen [4].

Analysis of the problem of relationships and responsibility shows the existence of different approaches to this phenomenon. In our country, some aspects of this topic were discussed by N.S. Safayev, D.G. Beknazarova, E.G. Goziev, V. Karimova. S.Kh. It was studied by such researchers as Nazarova, Z.T. Nishonova, B. Utanov, Sh.A. Eshmetov. In foreign psychology, V.N. Miyasishchev, expanding the essence of the concept of "relationships" in psychology, emphasized that the psychological meaning of relationships is one of the forms of reflection of the surrounding reality by a person. The formation of relationships within human relationships occurs as a result of the conscious reflection of the essence of objectively existing social relations of society in the macro- and microeconomic conditions in which it lives.

One of the first definitions of "psychological relations" was given by the researcher V.N. Taking into account the relationship as a connection of the individual with the external environment, belonging to Myasishchev, he emphasizes the dependence of the individual on the individually accumulated experience and history of the personality development. According to the author, "psychological relations of a person represent an integral system of individual, selected, conscious connections of a person with various aspects of objective reality in a developed form. This system originates from the entire history of human development, expresses his personal experience and determines his actions and experiences as his inner strength" [3]. In his concept, V.N. Myasishchev considers psychological relations from the point of view of different meanings: here relations in the general sense represent descriptions of the psyche, which are one. components of a number of structural elements of the general psyche: processes, qualities and states, and finally, one of the classes of psychological facts - defined as a psychological formation.

V. N. Miyashchev shows the role of relationships as a descriptive mechanism for determining human behavior. "Spirit is what allows us to plan in advance, adapt to certain things, wait until they manifest themselves in real actions" [3]. In his research, B. F. Lomov pays great attention to his understanding of the "personality-society" relationship, since he defined the nature of intervention in the system of social relations that determines the formation and disclosure of the psychological characteristics of the individual. That is, motives, aspirations, interests, etc. [5]. According to the author, this direction is closely related to relationships with others.

In his research, I.R. Sushkov understands the psychological attitude in the psychology of personal relationships as a measure of subjective change in events that can occur as a result of the interaction of the subject with the object, and this phenomenon is of great importance for human life. living organism [7]. The central category of the concept is the relationship between groups that arise as a result of their interaction. G.M. Andreeva said that the idea and concept of phenomena that experience behavioral determination is supported by various authors and primarily in the context of studying relationships.

G.M. Andreeva in her research identifies two types of relationship systems:

1st person social relations.

2nd person psychological relations.

The structure of social relations includes social, political, ideological and other types of relations, these people represent certain social groups. The author emphasizes the unfavorable nature of social relations, which are built depending on the position occupied in society, and the mutual understanding of certain social roles that oppose relationships based on relationships reflects its attitude based on the principle of antipathy. .

Psychological relations, according to G.M. Andreeva, "... the nature of interpersonal relations differs significantly from the nature of social relations: their most important characteristic is the emotional basis" [5].

The specifics of accepting and implementing responsibility are largely determined by its object. In conclusion, it should be noted that the development of responsibility relations in entrepreneurial activity determines the category of responsibility, which is distinguished by the social and moral-legal attitude of a person to society, the fulfillment of his moral duty and legal norms. As a result of developing the issue of responsibility in relations, it is possible to achieve high-quality efficiency in all areas of business activity.

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